

AI4

eosc

Second release of the AI Platform as a Service

Deliverable ID	D4.4 - Second release of the AI Platform as a Service
Work Package Reference	WP4
Issue	1.0
Due Date of Deliverable	31/08/2025
Submission Date	29/08/2025
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Lead Partner	INFN
Contributors	INFN, UPV, PREDICTIA, IISAS, LIP, CSIC, KIT
Grant Agreement No	101058593
Call ID	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	10.5281/zenodo.16737927
Website	https://ai4eosc.eu/

**Funded by
the European Union**

¹ **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services),
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services),
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Prepared by	Reviewed by	Approved by
A. Costantini (INFN)	I. Heredia (CSIC) Marta Obregón (CSIC)	Á. López (CSIC)

Issue	Date	Description	Author(s)
0.1	02/07/2025	Table of Content	Alessandro Costantini (INFN)
0.2	15/07/2025	Drafting of the deliverable	Alessandro Costantini (INFN), Miguel Caballer (UPV), Ignacio Heredia (CSIC), Amanda Calatrava (UPV), Germán Moltó (UPV), Miguel Caballer (UPV), Saúl Fernandez Tobias (CSIC), Judith Sáinz-Pardo (CSIC)
0.3	21/07/2025	Included information about AI as a Service and Developer Journeys regarding OSCAR	Amanda Calatrava (UPV), Germán Moltó (UPV), Miguel Caballer (UPV)
0.4	01/08/2025	Included information about different services	Alessandro Costantini (INFN), Miguel Caballer (UPV), Ignacio Heredia (CSIC), Judith Sáinz-Pardo (CSIC)
0.5	07/08/2025	Initial version of the complete deliverable	Alessandro Costantini (INFN)
0.6	21/08/2025	WP4 internal review	Alessandro Costantini (INFN)
0.7	25/08/2025	First external review	Ignacio Heredia (CSIC) Marta Obregón Ruiz (CSIC)
1.0	29/08/2025	Final review and acceptance by PMB	Alessandro Costantini (INFN)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES	4
LIST OF FIGURES	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1 - Introduction	6
1.1 - Objectives	6
1.2 - Architecture overview	7
2 - Status of AI4EOSC 2 implementation plan	7
3 - Infrastructure-centric Components	9
3.1 - PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning	10
Support for automatic deployment of the Workload Management System	10
PaaS components for provisioning - deployed components	11
3.2 - Workload Management System	16
Transition to WAN-based Consul Federation	16
Improved Token Management in Ansible Workflows	17
Raft State Backup Automation	17
Auxiliary Services and Maintenance	17
EOSC EU Node Integration	17
3.3 - AI as a Service	18
3.4 - Advanced AI Tools: Distributed and Federated training	20
3.5 - Interactive developments tools	24
4 - Developer Journeys to the infrastructure	26
4.1 - Join a resource federation via the INDIGO PaaS Orchestration service	26
4.2 - Deploy a Sync&Share storage solution based on NextCloud	27
4.3 - Deploy a Nomad cluster	30
4.4 - Join my resources to the Nomad production cluster	32
Automated configuration using Ansible	33
4.5 - Deploy an OSCAR cluster	34
5 - Conclusion	37
References	38

LIST OF TABLES

- **Table 1:** Components and actions: status and description.
- **Table 2:** Additional CVAT services by AI4EOSC.
- **Table 3:** Periodic backup of CVAT configuration.

LIST OF FIGURES

- **Figure 1:** AI4EOSC platform
- **Figure 2:** AI Platform as a Service components and interactions with the other components of the project
- **Figure 3:** Consul WAN gossip architecture scheme
- **Figure 4:** PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning components
- **Figure 5:** INDIGO-PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning micro-services.
- **Figure 6:** AI platform customization via resource orchestration
- **Figure 7:** Screenshot of the Grafana dashboard for the AI4EOSC OSCAR cluster.
- **Figure 8:** Screenshots of the new OSCAR dashboard.
- **Figure 9:** Tools available in the AI4EOSC dashboard for FL (Flower and NVFlare).
- **Figure 10:** Privacy options available when deploying the Flower FL server.
- **Figure 11:** Functionality for monitoring CO2 emissions in the FL Flower tool.
- **Figure 12:** FL with NVFlare in AI4EOSC, NVFlare configuration example.
- **Figure 13:** Example of NVFlare dashboard. Extracted from X.
- **Figure 14:** View of the resource providers configuration from the PaaS Dashboard.
- **Figure 15:** View of the user deployments and type from the PaaS Dashboard.
- **Figure 16:** View of the Sync&Share service from the PaaS Dashboard.
- **Figure 17:** Sync&Share scheduling type.
- **Figure 18:** Sync&Share customization interface.
- **Figure 19:** User-specific deployment via Orchestrator Dashboard component.
- **Figure 20:** user-specific deployment and options.

- **Figure 21:** View of the Nomad configuration from the PaaS Dashboard.
- **Figure 22:** View of the Nomad Join configuration from the IM-Dashboard.
- **Figure 23:** List of catalogues of templates from the IM-Dashboard.
- **Figure 24:** View of the cloud providers from the IM-Dashboard.
- **Figure 25:** View of the configuration about the OSCAR cluster from the IM-Dashboard.
- **Figure 26:** View of the OSCAR deployment information from the IM-Dashboard.
- **Figure 27:** View of the OSCAR dashboard.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable outlines the status of the different components and functionalities operated within WP4 during the second part of the AI4EOSC project that are an integral part of the AI4EOSC second release (AI4EOSC 2nd Release). From there, the definition of the functionalities of the AI4EOSC 2nd Release are depicted.

Specifically, the architecture of the different components is detailed, including the status and description of the platform components, where updates and new features have been described.

The document also contains a section to provide a description of the main service workflow deployment when interacting with the infrastructure components.

1 - INTRODUCTION

1.1 - OBJECTIVES

During the second half of the AI4EOSC project, activities have been continued to improve components and functionalities of the AI4EOSC platform to be provided to the final users. Initially collected and described in the deliverable D4.1 [[AI4EOSC-D4.1](#)], in the deliverable D4.2 [[AI4EOSC-D4.2](#)] we described the work carried out on each of them, as well as the deviations from the initially defined plan. The deliverable D4.3 [[AI4EOSC-D4.3](#)], instead, reported a status update of the services and tools that had been included in the AI4EOSC 2nd Release.

The present deliverable reports a status update of the services and tools since the previous demonstrators, providing an overview of the functionalities of the services that are part of the AI4EOSC 2nd Release.

The document is structured as follows.

In [Section 2](#) we report the status of the different components, including their implementation.

In [Section 3](#) we explain the updates related to each component of the infrastructure, with a summary of the current status of each component.

In [Section 4](#) we describe some major examples of application deployment, focusing on the developers' perspective.

In [Section 5](#) we draw the conclusions.

1.2 - ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

This section provides an overview of the architectural updates of the related components developed by WP4. In particular the present deliverable will address updates related to the following macro components (see [Figure 1](#) for details):

- PaaS orchestration and provisioning,
- AI as a Service,
- AI4EOSC platform related components.

Figure 1: C4 diagram of the AI4EOSC platform²

2 - STATUS OF AI4EOSC 2 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

This section evaluates how the roadmap stated in the Deliverable D4.3 has been realized so far, specifying when changes from the plan have occurred. To do so, [Table 1](#) shows the different components and actions implemented for the AI4EOSC 2nd Release and their status and description. In order to detail the level of compliance or implementation of the different actions or components, in [Table 1](#) the green bullet (●)

² Original figure:

https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#ai4eosc_view

represents that the component is ready, the blue bullet (●) that it is under testing phase, and the orange one (●) that it is under development or is a prototype.

Table 1: Components and actions: status and description. Green bullet: component ready; blue bullet: component under testing; orange bullet: component under development or prototype.

Component/Actions	Status + Description
Federated Service Catalogue/ design and implementation	● The service has been implemented and has been integrated in the second release.
PaaS Monitoring and Metering/design and implementation	● The service has been implemented and has been integrated in the second release.
PaaS Orchestrator/Nomad deployment	● The automatic deployment of Nomad + Consul has been designed and implemented in the PaaS Orchestrator. Minor fixes have been implemented.
PaaS Orchestrator/OSCAR deployment	● The automatic deployment of OSCAR on top of Kubernetes has been designed and implemented in the PaaS Orchestrator. MinIO object storage service has been also implemented in the related environment. Minor fixes have been implemented.
PaaS Orchestrator/Federated Catalogue integration	● The service has been integrated and made available in the second release. The information to be integrated in the Federated Catalogue has been defined and the initial version of the catalogue has been populated.
Cloud Provider Ranker/algorithm update	● The datasource have been identified and the related dataset has been defined. AI-based algorithms have been selected and are part of the final release.
Infrastructure Manager automation + OSCAR integration	● OSCAR components automation has been implemented via the IM. The IM can deploy OSCAR services defined in TOSCA templates.
OSCAR manager/Reduced cold start	● To mitigate cold start, a method for prefetching Docker images in the Kubernetes nodes when creating an OSCAR service has been implemented.
OSCAR Manager/Interfaces + Libraries	● The following features have been integrated in OSCAR: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deployment of services that expose their own API as an OSCAR service. ● Initial multitenancy support.

Component/Actions	Status + Description
Workload Management System implementation and automation	● Nomad and Consul infrastructures have been deployed and Traefik has been used as load balancer.
Interactive Development environment	● VScode and JupyterLab have been integrated as the two available interactive development environments (IDEs) and can be used throughout the platform.
CVAT integration for image labelling	● CVAT has been integrated as an open-source tool for image and video annotation provided as a cloud application.

3 - INFRASTRUCTURE-CENTRIC COMPONENTS

In the present section we report an overview of the improvements carried out about technologies and solutions chosen for each of the components. In addition, in [Figure 2](#) the architecture of the platform together with its components and their relations is presented, highlighting the WP4 tasks involved.

Figure 2: AI Platform as a Service components and interactions with the other components of the project

[[INDIGO-PaaS Orchestrator](#)]. This ensures that the deployment process is fast, reliable, and repeatable, reducing the risk of errors and minimising the time and effort required for manual deployment. Furthermore, the TOSCA templates also enable the deployment of the main components of the AI4EOSC platform: the API and Dashboard, enabling users to deploy their own instance of the AI4EOSC software stack.

The TOSCA templates have been modified, tested and promoted to production to be used with IM via the PaaS orchestrator. The list of the TOSCA templates in production is the following:

- Single VM deployment with persistent volume, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator) [[DeploymentPaaSVM](#)]
- Docker container with persistent volume, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator) [[DeploymentPaaS Docker](#)]
- Nomad+Consul, Latest release (IM) [[DeploymentIMNomad](#)]
- Nomad+Consul, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator) [[DeploymentPaaSNomad](#)]
- OSCAR, Latest release (IM) [[DeploymentIMOSCAR](#)]
- OSCAR, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator) [[DeploymentPaaSOSCAR](#)]
- Nomad+Consul merging existing cluster (IM) [[DeploymentIMNomad+](#)]
- Nomad+Consul merging existing cluster (PaaS Orchestrator) [[DeploymentPaaSNomad+](#)]
- NextCloud deployment (PaaS Orchestrator) [[DeploymentPaaSNextCloud](#)]

PaaS components for provisioning - deployed components

The INDIGO-PaaS Orchestration and provisioning service leverages on different micro-services that are depicted in [Figure 5](#) together with the related interactions.

Figure 5: INDIGO-PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning micro-services. Details about each component are provided in Deliverable D4.4.

PaaS AAI mechanism

The Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure service for the PaaS components layer is provided by the INDIGO Identity and Access Management Service [\[INDIGO-IAM\]](#) (INDIGO-IAM) that leverages the OpenID Connect and OAuth2.0 [\[OIDC, OAuth2.0\]](#) protocols. The updates and improvements to the service are listed below:

- Integration of MFA with external OIDC and SAML
- Integration MFA with x.509 authentication
- Added logging of the outcome of a VOMS proxy request Upgrade dependencies and minor cleanups
- Added a PATCH replace operation to SCIM Group endpoint
- Supported no mandatory notes on registration
- Supported DER & URL-Encoded PEM client certificates
- Added support for voperson_id claim in the AARC JWT profile
- Added support for resource parameter
- Added the number of active users
- Added endpoint to search users by their authority
- Allowed to customize the email subject prefix
- Assigned oidc-agent clients ownership to the whom approved it
- Added AUP exemption for service accounts
- Added a READER role that gives read access to users and groups info
- Supported JDBC session on same db

Infrastructure Manager (IM)

The Infrastructure Manager is an open-source framework designed to simplify the access and usability of IaaS clouds. It automates the selection, deployment, configuration, monitoring and update of virtualized infrastructures.

- Enabled to restrict the set of TOSCA files to be processed.
- Added OAI-PMH support, showing the list of TOSCA files enabled.
- Migrated from AppDB to the new cloud-info-api
- Integrated with the new DyDNS API to add and remove host names.
- Fixed error deleting IM security groups in OpenStack.
- Added a function to return public IPs and GPUs in EstimateResources

PaaS Orchestrator

Built with Java technologies and on the open-source workflow manager “Flowable” [\[Flowable\]](#), the Orchestrator [\[INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator Release\]](#) allows federating heterogeneous resource providers and orchestrate the deployment of TOSCA templates, selecting the best provider according to criteria like the data location, the

Service Level Agreement (SLA) and monitoring information. It provides a set of APIs to create, monitor and manage the deployments.

The Orchestrator has been updated with the following improvements:

- The possibility to manage the creation/deletion of IAM clients via Orchestrator. The INDIGO-IAM [\[INDIGO-IAM\]](#) client resource is completely managed by the Orchestrator: when a user submits the request of creation of a deployment requiring an INDIGO-IAM client, the Orchestrator creates the client, and when the user triggers the deletion of the deployment, the Orchestrator deletes the corresponding INDIGO-IAM client;
- Added a parameter to force the deletion of a deployment. This may not delete some resources, for example IAM clients;
- Added a group authorization. Now the check is directly performed by the Orchestrator that stops the user's request when the used group is not allowed for the user;
- Added skipping monitoring workflow when the monitoring url is not specified;
- Metadata has been enriched with the information of preferred_username, which is contained in the user's token;
- Added the integration with the AI-Ranker. The Orchestrator reads the messages of a specific queue of the Kafka instance to retrieve the list of providers ordered by the AI-Ranker [\[AIRanker, PR-64\]](#).

INDOGO PaaS Dashboard

The INDIGO PaaS Dashboard [\[INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator Dashboard Release\]](#) is a Flask [\[Flask\]](#) application with a SQL database (MySQL [\[MySQL\]](#)) that enables users to interact easily with the services of the PaaS, particularly the Orchestrator, to create TOSCA-based deployments. The dashboard provides a user-friendly interface for managing and monitoring deployments (see [Figure 6](#) for more details). Here the main feature/updated to the service:

- Updated usage statistics section;
- Added hot fixes for admins sections;
- Added a functionality to add administrators defined by membership in an IAM group;
- Added multiselection for provider, status, group;
- Added a filter on flavor based on TOSCA constraints;
- Added IAM group selection from Dashboard;
- Added GPU info in flavors.

Federation Registry

Efforts have been made to replace the Service Level Agreement Tool (SLAT) and the Configuration Management Database (CMDDB) for several reasons, in particular because they are outdated tools with vulnerabilities. Thus, two new tools have been developed: the Federation Registry [[FederationRegistry](#), [FederationRegistryRelease](#)], that is a Python web application providing public REST API to inspect the configurations of the federated providers, and the Federation Registry Feeder [[FederationRegistryFeeder](#)], that is a Python script used to populate the Federation Registry. The PaaS Orchestrator is fully compliant with these two tools that have been integrated into the INDIGO PaaS Orchestration system.

Changes for Federation Registry:

- Integrated fedreg-lib.
- Updated dependencies.
- Updated jenkins pipelines.
- Added functionality: each flavor belongs to a unique service.
- Added network support for multiple projects.

Changes for Federation Registry Feeder

- Integrated fedreg-lib.
- Updated dependencies.
- Updated jenkins pipelines.
- Added network support for multiple projects.
- Each flavor belongs to a unique service.
- Add new information to the feeder message sent to kafka.
- Update kafka connection to use SSL.
-

Kafka

A Kafka [[Kafka](#)] instance has been deployed to collect useful information for the AI-Ranker from a heterogeneous set of sources, organized into different topics. It also allows the Orchestrator to read the list of providers ranked by the AI-Ranker. In particular:

- The airanker-dataset topic gathers the data used by the AI-Ranker to train ML models.
- The providers-to-rank topic contains the messages on which the AI-Ranker performs inference.
- The ranked-providers topic stores the ordered lists of providers produced by the AI-Ranker.

AI-Ranker

AI-Ranker [AIRanker, AIRankerRelease] has been designed and implemented to overcome the limits of the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator in determining which provider to use to submit a deployment. In the original version of the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator, in fact, the ranking was based on an ordered list of providers, selected according to the group the user belonged to.

The AI-Ranker, based on MLFlow [MLFlow], is performing both training and inference of Machine Learning models using the messages read from specific Kafka topics. The ranked list of providers is generated by the AI-ranker by combining the prediction of deployment success/failure with the estimated deployment creation time.

The new AI-based INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator has been integrated with the AI-Ranker to optimize resource usage adopting Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques.

Changes for AI-Ranker:

- Code refactoring.
- Added tests.
- Added extended README.
- Updated consumer and producer to use SSL communication with Kafka.

Figure 6: AI platform customization via resource orchestration. Here the different steps: (i) the user access the INDIGO PaaS via the PaaS Dashboard via the INDIGO IAM (ii) service; (iii) select and (iv) configure

the service to deploy; access the service (v) and (vi) via the credential and endpoint provided by the orchestrator system.

3.2 - WORKLOAD MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Following the previous release, a set of targeted improvements has been completed to enhance the stability, security, and maintainability of the federated cloud environment. These changes reinforce the robustness of the platform's orchestration layer and streamline its operation across federated sites.

Transition to WAN-based Consul Federation

Figure 3: Consul WAN gossip architecture scheme

The federation strategy for Consul has been updated to follow a WAN gossip architecture ([Figure 3](#)). In contrast to the previous LAN-based approach, where Consul clients required direct connectivity with servers across all datacenters, the new model restricts client communication to local Consul servers only. Inter-datacenter communication is now handled exclusively at the server level, which:

- Eliminates issues caused by private subnet separation between sites.
- Improves stability by avoiding temporary disconnections of Consul clients.
- Simplifies network requirements across sites.

Improved Token Management in Ansible Workflows

The deployment process has been enhanced to address issues in Consul and Nomad token handling during Ansible-based automation. Previously, a placeholder mechanism was used to insert tokens into configuration templates before the tokens were generated, which led to Molecule idempotency test failures.

The Ansible roles have been restructured to:

- Delay service configuration until valid tokens are available.
- Eliminate placeholder values from templates.
- Ensure clean and idempotent deployments validated by automated testing.

Raft State Backup Automation

The system now includes an automated mechanism for backing up the Raft consensus state used by Consul. This feature is essential to protect the integrity of the federation in the event of datacenter failures or network partitions. The backup process is executed periodically, storing consistent snapshots of the Raft state that can be used to restore the cluster quickly and safely when needed. This enhancement significantly reduces the complexity and downtime associated with recovery procedures, improving the platform's overall resilience.

Auxiliary Services and Maintenance

A set of auxiliary functionalities has been developed to support the operation and maintenance of the Nomad-based WMS:

- **Email Notification Service:** Notifies users when long-queued jobs are finally deployed.
- **Docuum:** Manages disk space by applying an LRU (Least Recently Used) policy to Docker images.
- **Maintenance Jobs:** Periodic tasks are executed to:
 - Empty the trash folder in Docker containers.
 - Remove Nomad jobs that have been dead for a long time.
 - Delete pending jobs that are not in queued, starting, or unknown states.

EOSC EU Node Integration

To increase the amount of resources available in the platform and demonstrate how to integrate resources from other cloud providers we have completed a proof-of-concept that shows we can easily add and manage resources from the EOSC EU Node. This integration was performed using our advanced orchestration and automation tools, demonstrating our ability to seamlessly incorporate a diverse set of cloud computing resources that is currently spanning a diverse set of providers (including academic providers, HPC centers and commercial providers). This not only makes our platform more robust but also helps both us and the EOSC EU Node operators better understand the technical requirements for integration.

Here is what this means:

- **Better Scalability:** Our platform can now handle more resources, making it easier to grow and adapt to the needs of the scientific community.
- **More Resource Options:** By adding resources from the EOSC EU Node, we've expanded the tools and data available on our platform, fostering more innovation and collaboration.
- **Better Compatibility:** This integration shows that different resources can work together smoothly, which is key for driving open science forward.

3.3 - AI AS A SERVICE

In AI4EOSC, OSCAR acts as a key component for delivering AI models as a service. It enables rapid deployment and seamless scaling on auto-scaled Kubernetes clusters, while offering a user-friendly and efficient framework for performing AI model inference.

The key implementations since the last deliverable are the following:

- **Accounting module updates:** AI models' usage metrics are obtained through Prometheus [[Prometheus](#)] as monitoring platform resource usage, and GoAccess [[GoAccess](#)] for collecting geolocation data and service-related metrics as reported in D4.3. Following the recent updates, detailed information has been added to track which specific users are deploying and running services, as well as their country of origin. Moreover, metrics are now visualized through a Grafana [[Grafana](#)] panel, providing a more intuitive and visually accessible view of the cluster's status. [Figure 7](#) shows a screenshot of the AI4EOSC's OSCAR Grafana dashboard⁴ to illustrate the information that can be found.

⁴ AI4EOSC OSCAR metrics.

<https://oscargrycap.grafana.net/public-dashboards/a7a4142a62e7487ba53270bf44640bcb?orgId=1>

Figure 7: Screenshot of the Grafana dashboard for the AI4EOSC OSCAR cluster.

- Enforced multi-tenancy and privacy on the OSCAR cluster:** Part of the effort on the implementation during this last period has been focused on enhancing the privacy of sensitive data that can be used within the platform.
 - Secrets:** Since the inference runs in a containerized environment, sensitive data that needs to be used during execution of the services is injected through Kubernetes secrets to be visible only within the container and the user-defined script.
 - Bucket Management:**
 - All services and storage buckets are set to private by default, ensuring a secure data storage environment where access is restricted, unless explicitly granted.
 - The OSCAR Manager API handles interactions with MinIO within the OSCAR platform, which supports full CRUD operations. This approach decouples the OSCAR Dashboard from direct interaction with MinIO [MinIO] storage operations, enabling centralized management of access policies and permissions from the OSCAR Manager API.
- New Dashboard:** A redesign of the OSCAR interface has been introduced, built with React [React] technology, enhancing performance, responsiveness, and overall usability. In Figure 8 some sections of the new interface are shown.

Figure 8: Screenshots of the new OSCAR dashboard.

- **Keycloak integration:** With the transition to using Keycloak [Keycloak] for user management, the OSCAR platform has been fully integrated with the project's Keycloak instance to streamline authentication and access control. Additionally, the UPV team has begun deploying its own dedicated Keycloak instance to enhance platform testing and accessibility for multitenancy.
- **OSCAR Batch:** Due to the needs of use cases of the platform, especially the ones coming from the iMagine project, we implemented a new tool, designed to perform batch-based processing using an OSCAR service. OSCAR Batch⁵ features a coordinator service that manages the distribution of image processing tasks. Users supply a MinIO bucket with the files to be processed, and the coordinator determines the optimal level of parallelism based on available cluster resources. It then efficiently allocates the workload across multiple service instances to maximize performance.
- **Acceptance tests via the Robot framework:** to validate that the OSCAR clusters behave as expected, we have implemented a testing pipeline for OSCAR with the Robot Framework [Robot]. This pipeline is automatically and periodically executed in a Jenkins [Jenkins AI4EO SC] instance, and sends an email to the developers if any test fails to be completed, thus ensuring CI/CD in the components of the AI4EO SC platform. This acceptance testing is enforced as part of the development of OSCAR to automatically assess that new developments do not break previous functionality.

3.4 - ADVANCED AI TOOLS: DISTRIBUTED AND FEDERATED TRAINING

As detailed in previous deliverables, one of the main objectives within this WP (specifically regarding Task 4.4), concerns the integration of advanced AI tools to be exploited by the platform users.

⁵ OSCAR Batch, <https://github.com/grycap/oscar-batch>

Starting from what has been developed in D4.3 [AI4EOSC-D4.3], the work has been enriched by providing the users with facilities to carry out distributed training of their models (for which guides and tutorials have been included in the documentation, taking advantage of the *horovod* [Horovod] Python library for distributing the training in multiple GPUs from a single node), as well as to perform incremental (online) learning.

However, the main tool developed and integrated in the platform in this sense is federated learning. As already exposed in previous deliverables, with FL users can carry out the training of their models in a distributed (federated) way, with data stored in different computational nodes, either in the platform itself, in their local machines or in external cloud providers. All this can be orchestrated exploiting the AI4EOSC platform, specifically deploying an FL server from the platform.

In this way, a tool has been included in the platform that allows the deployment of an FL server using the Flower [Flower] library. In addition, as detailed in D4.3, several extensions have been implemented to make this framework work successfully on the platform as well as to improve some of its functionalities. However, the major milestone since D4.3 in this regard has been the integration of a second FL software, NVFlare [NVflare] (powered by NVIDIA), thus allowing users to choose the framework that best suits their particular needs (see [Figure 9](#) for details).

Figure 9: Tools available in the AI4EOSC dashboard for FL (Flower and NVFlare).

The following are the new extensions deployed for Flower's FL server in addition to the ones detailed in D4.2 and D4.3 (which included: allowing to run the server behind a proxy, development of a client authentication service based in tokens, and integration of new aggregation strategies than can be selected from the dashboard when deploying the server).

- **Integration of Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) from the server side.** Users are allowed to introduce differential privacy (DP) from the server side in a quite simple way. Specifically, as depicted in [Figure 10](#), when deploying the server, users have the option to select whether they want to add DP, and if so, they only need to enter the noise multiplier, the clipping norm, and the number of sampled clients. In the same line, we also allow the use of metric privacy, as defined in the Z for FL, following the metric defined in that paper in order to prevent client inference attacks on the aggregated model. For this second version we have implemented a new class that inherits from the corresponding Flower class for server side DP. This has been included in the AI4EOSC GitHub

repository of Flower [\[AI4EOSC/flower\]](#) (forked from the original one and maintained with the new extensions), in a dedicated branch.

The screenshot shows the 'Federated configuration' step of the Flower FL server configuration. The interface includes a progress bar with three steps: 'General configuration', 'Hardware configuration', and 'Federated configuration'. The 'Federated options' section contains:

- Number of rounds: 5
- Evaluation metric: accuracy
- Number of minimum clients (fit): 2
- Number of minimum clients (available): 2
- Federated aggregation strategy: Federated Averaging (FedAvg)

 The 'Privacy options' section includes:

- Metric privacy: false
- Noise multiplier: 1
- Number of sampled clients: 2
- Clipping norm: 0.1
- Differential privacy: checked

 At the bottom right, there are 'Back' and 'Submit' buttons.

Figure 10: Privacy options available when deploying the Flower FL server (last step of the configuration).

- Carbon footprint monitoring.** Within the commitment to developing sustainable solutions, it is particularly important for users to be able to monitor the emissions of their training. While the integration of state-of-the-art carbon footprint monitoring tools (e.g. codecarbon or perun) is straightforward via simple decorations or calls to such libraries, this has a slightly higher complexity when the environment is federated, as each client's emissions must be sent to the server for aggregation along with the server's own. In order to facilitate this, from the dashboard (see [Figure 11](#) for details) the users can select if they want to monitor the training emissions, and at the same time, it is included in the AI4OS docs [\[DocsFlower\]](#) the (minimal) changes that must be made from the clients to allow such monitoring.

The screenshot shows the 'Federated configuration' step of the Flower FL server configuration. The progress bar highlights 'Federated configuration' as the active step. The 'Deployment options' section includes:

- Deployment title: (empty text input)
- Deployment description: (empty text input)
- Monitor CO2 emissions: checked

 The 'Service to run' section has radio buttons for 'Fedserver' (selected), 'Jupyter', and 'Vscode'. The 'Docker options' section includes:

- Docker image: ai4oshub/ai4os-federated-server
- Docker tag: latest

 At the top right, there is a 'Show help' button.

Figure 11: Functionality for monitoring CO2 emissions in the FL Flower tool.

- New aggregation strategy.** Additionally, we have proposed in [\[FedAvgOpt\]](#) a new aggregation strategy, *FedAvgOpt*, which has been integrated for using it in Flower and that can be selected directly from the dashboard.

Regarding AI advanced tools development, one of the main achievements in this last period of the project is the integration of NVFlare within the platform.

Figure 12: FL with NVFlare in AI4EOSC, NVFlare configuration example.

Specifically, for deploying the NVFLARE Dashboard, users only need to introduce the NVFlare credentials for the admin (email and password). See [Figure 12](#) and [Figure 13](#) for details. The dashboard allows the creation of startup kits which are essential for the proper initialization and secure connection of the components of the FL system (FL servers, FL clients and admin clients). The startup kit includes the configuration files and certificates required for establishing secure communication.

Figure 13: Example of NVFlare dashboard. After successful login, the project admin can run the project by starting the sites authorized and connecting them to the server hosted on the platform.

In addition, when deploying this tool, users can log on to the SERVER-JUPYTER, which provides access to a JupyterLab environment for the server. Within the NVFlare ecosystem, a project can have multiple admins (an admin must create the deployment in the AI4EOSC platform) and each organization participating in the federated training should also designate an Organization Admin, which will be in charge of registering

their own organization’s sites. The Organization Admins can access the dashboard through and sign up to register themselves and their sites. Then they must be approved by one project administrator.

The main novelty of this tool is that from the dashboard (once the configuration process has been carried out with the corresponding files in each case for the secure connection), the project admin can run the project by starting the sites authorized and connecting them to the server hosted on the platform. Thus, there is no need for clients to “start” themselves but everything can be orchestrated from the NVFlare dashboard. Once a sufficient number of sites are connected to the server, any Admin can log in to the console and submit an FL job.

Details on the use of the NVFlare tool and how to run a FL job are given in the documentation [\[DocsNVFlare\]](#). In addition, it’s interesting to note that with NVFlare we allow users also to take advantage of other distributed learning architectures, including vertical FL, which can be seen as a kind of split learning.

Finally, concerning the exploitation of these two tools by the project use cases, this is reflected in the form of two publications applying FL to use case 1 (agrometeorology) using Flower [\[FLUC1\]](#), and to use case 3 (automated thermography) using NVFlare [\[FLUC3\]](#).

3.5 - INTERACTIVE DEVELOPMENTS TOOLS

During the current reporting period, the integration of CVAT into the AI4EOSC platform was completed, tested, refined, and made available to users as a tool accessible via the Dashboard. The integration process involved several iterations, beginning with CVAT version 2.7.3, advancing through version 2.25.0, and concluding with version 2.28.0.

The core of the CVAT integration is a Nomad job specification⁶, developed by adapting the original CVAT Docker Compose configuration. This Nomad job ensures the correct configuration and deployment of all 14 CVAT components as individual Nomad tasks, their isolation from other CVAT instances, and networking configuration. These tasks include advanced analytics and monitoring features based on Vector, ClickHouse, and Grafana. Additionally, it incorporates four AI4EOSC-specific tasks—*share*, *synclocal*, *syncremote*, and *backups*—to extend CVAT functionality (see [Table 2](#)).

Table 2: Additional CVAT services by AI4EOSC.

Nomad task name	Description
share	Enables seamless access to Nextcloud remote storage by mounting volumes as local paths within task containers.
synclocal	Restores the CVAT instance from a backup stored on remote storage.
syncremote	Creates a backup of the CVAT instance on remote storage upon shutdown.

⁶ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-papi/blob/master/etc/tools/ai4os-cvat/nomad.hcl>

Nomad task name	Description
backups	Performs periodic backups of CVAT projects and associated annotations.

The backups task utilizes CVAT API to create backup of projects or annotations, and cron for scheduling the backups. It includes a sweeper program to automatically clean obsolete backups and thus save storage space. The sweeper can be configured to keep the minimal number of backups and to keep the backups for a minimal period of time while considering the maximum number of backups. Within the AI4EOSC platform, the periodic backup system has been configured as described in [Table 3](#). The implementation of the periodic backup system with all the configuration options explained is available in GitHub [\[CVAT1\]](#).

In relation to the planned persistence enabler, an alternative approach was adopted due to performance and caching issues encountered when mounting remote storage as local volumes. Instead, a less network-intensive, shutdown-triggered full backup mechanism was implemented. This solution performs a complete backup of the active CVAT instance and uploads it to a designated backup directory on the remote storage. The implementation adheres to the official CVAT backup procedure [\[CVAT2\]](#), with full automation integrated into the process. The use of remote storage as locally mounted volumes has not been entirely deprecated; rather, it is utilized specifically for the shared path [\[CVAT3\]](#) configuration in CVAT.

Table 3: Periodic backup of CVAT configuration.

Parameter	Value	Description
CVAT_BACKUP_TTL_HOURS	24	minimum age of backup file in hours; if the age of the backup file exceeds this value and there are more than $\${CVAT_MIN_NUM_BACKUPS}$ backup files, this backup is deleted by the sweeper
CVAT_MIN_NUM_BACKUPS	3	minimum number of backup files to keep regardless of their age ($\${CVAT_BACKUP_TTL}$)
CVAT_BACKUP_SAVE_IMAGES	false	whether to store images along with annotations
CVAT_BACKUP_REQUEST_TIME_OUT_HOURS	1	maximum time in hours to wait for CVAT to prepare a backup

Additional modifications [\[CVAT4\]](#) were required also to CVAT [\[CVAT5\]](#) itself. These included configuration adjustments, automated superuser provisioning, and enhancements to the original Dockerfile to incorporate the rclone⁷ tool for integration with Nextcloud remote storage.

⁷ rclone official page. <https://rclone.org/>

4 - DEVELOPER JOURNEYS TO THE INFRASTRUCTURE

In the present section, an overview of the different deployments models and services are presented and described, highlighting the easiness of the procedures implemented via both the PaaS Orchestrator system, to properly select federated resources, or directly via the IM.

4.1 - JOIN A RESOURCE FEDERATION VIA THE INDIGO PaaS ORCHESTRATION SERVICE

Resource Federation has been one of the tasks carried out during the project lifetime.

The federation of computing resources, in fact, represents a strategic advancement in digital infrastructure, offering substantial added value for collaborative research and innovation. By enabling seamless integration of geographically and institutionally diverse computing environments, federation enhances scalability, resilience, and operational efficiency.

In such respect, the INDIGO PaaS Orchestration and provisioning system can support multiple resource providers (see [Figure 14](#) for details).

To this end, procedures have been standardized and made available as a set of guides [[AI4EOSCResourceFed](#)] that the resource provider must follow in order to make the computing resources - and related services - available to the AI4EOSC federation.

The procedure relies on common standards such the OIDC/OAuth protocols and a set of standard REST API provided by the different software solutions used.

As soon as the provider has been federated, the Service Level Agreement can be defined among the provider and the user/community in order to use the resources made available.

As an added value, a new functionality has been added to the Orchestrator Dashboard component aimed at providing information about the number and type of submitted (and running) deployments submitted by the users. In such respect, [Figure 15](#) is showing the distribution of the deployment over the users and the federated providers.

The screenshot shows the 'Resource providers' configuration page in the PaaS Dashboard. The page has a dark blue sidebar with 'Dashboard' at the top and 'DEPLOYMENTS', 'ADVANCED', and 'ADMIN' below. The main content area is titled 'Resource providers' and shows a table with 7 entries. The table has three columns: 'SITE', 'SERVICE TYPE', and 'SERVICE ENDPOINT'. The entries are as follows:

SITE	SERVICE TYPE	SERVICE ENDPOINT
INFN-CNAF_ai4eoscc - tier1	org.openstack.neutron	https://cloud-api-pub.cz.cnaf.infn.it:9696/v2.0
INFN-CNAF_ai4eoscc - tier1	org.openstack.nova	https://cloud-api-pub.cz.cnaf.infn.it:8774/v2.1
INFN-CNAF_ai4eoscc - tier1	org.openstack.cinder	https://cloud-api-pub.cz.cnaf.infn.it:8776/v3
RECA-BARI_ai4eoscc - RegionOne	org.openstack.swift-s3	https://swift.recas.ba.infn.it:443
RECA-BARI_ai4eoscc - RegionOne	org.openstack.cinder	https://cinder.recas.ba.infn.it:443/v3
RECA-BARI_ai4eoscc - RegionOne	org.openstack.neutron	https://neutron.recas.ba.infn.it:443/v2.0
RECA-BARI_ai4eoscc - RegionOne	org.openstack.nova	https://nova.recas.ba.infn.it/v2.1

Showing 1 to 7 of 7 entries

Figure 14: View of the resource providers configuration from the PaaS Dashboard.

Figure 15: View of the user deployments and type from the PaaS Dashboard.

4.2 - DEPLOY A SYNC&SHARE STORAGE SOLUTION BASED ON NEXTCLOUD

The Sync&Share storage solution based on NextCloud [NextCloud] is offered to AI4EOSC Cloud users as a means to easily share documentation and user data among a project or a scientific collaboration.

As an added value, it is possible to integrate the application with any OIDC SSO system to grant access to a particular community.

The deployment of the Sync&Share solution within the AI4EOSC federation is fully automated using Ansible [Ansible], an open-source configuration management tool designed to simplify the provisioning and orchestration of infrastructure. Ansible works by executing sets of instructions, called playbooks, which describe the desired system configuration using a human-readable YAML syntax.

The deployment process is fully managed via the AI4EOSC PaaS orchestrator dashboard component where the user, having proper access and grants, can select the Sync&Share deployment as from Figure 16.

Figure 16: View of the Sync&Share service from the PaaS Dashboard.

After the service selection, the user can select either Automatic or Manual scheduling as shown in [Figure 17](#).

Scheduling STEP 2/4

SCHEDULING TYPE

Automatic
 Manual

Select a deployment provider or let the system choose automatically

CANCEL ← Back **CONTINUE** →

Figure 17: Sync&Share scheduling type.

In the first case, the PaaS Orchestration System will take care of choosing the best available provider, in the other case it will perform a direct submission towards one of the providers available, to be selected from the drop-down menu. In the case of manual scheduling, the flavors displayed on the next page will be those offered by the chosen provider.

After that, the user can customize the service by filling the configuration parameters as from [Figure 18](#).

DEPLOYMENT DESCRIPTION (0/50)

Description

GENERAL IMPLEMENTATION (ADVANCED) ADVANCED

DOCKER STORAGE SIZE

20

GB

Size of the volume to be mounted in /var/lib/docker

CONTACT EMAIL

Insert your Email for receiving notifications

ADMIN USERNAME

admin

Username for admin access

ADMIN PASSWORD

Password for admin user

MONITORING ADMIN USERNAME

admin

Username for the admin user of the monitoring service

MONITORING ADMIN PASSWORD

Password for the admin user of the monitoring service

BACKUP PASSPHRASE

Password for backup

DATA BUCKET NAME

Name of the bucket used to store data

BACKUP BUCKET NAME

Name of the bucket used by the monitoring system

IAM URL

https://iam.cloud.infn.it/

IAM url

IAM AUTHORIZED GROUP

IAM group authorized to access the service

FLAVOR

--Select--

Number of vCPUs and memory size of the Virtual Machine

Warning! You have not filled some mandatory fields. Please check the red boxes in each tab.

CANCEL

CONTINUE

Figure 18: Sync&Share customization interface.

As soon as the deployment is submitted, the deployment request is sent to the INDIGO PaaS Orchestration System. The deployment request can be monitored via the Orchestrator Dashboard from the "My deployments" page. As soon as the deployment is ready, the user will receive a notification by email (see [Figure 19](#) for more details).

Figure19: User-specific deployment via Orchestrator Dashboard component.

If the creation of a deployment fails, an additional option (retry) is introduced in the dropdown menu, allowing the user to resubmit the deployment with the same parameters, as from [Figure 20](#).

Figure 20: User-specific deployment and options.

As soon as the service is deployed in the underlying infrastructure, the user can retrieve the details of the deployment including the endpoint where to reach the Sync&Share service.

4.3 - DEPLOY A NOMAD CLUSTER

Automated configuration using Ansible

The deployment of a Nomad cluster within the AI4EOSC federation is fully automated using Ansible. For this specific case, a set of customized Ansible roles (available in the

project's GitHub repository⁸) has been developed to deploy and configure all the necessary components: Nomad, Consul, and Traefik [Traefik].

The deployment process begins with the preparation of a host inventory file, which defines all the nodes that will form part of the cluster. This includes specifying the Nomad and Consul master nodes, CPU and GPU clients, a Traefik node (responsible for service routing), and optionally nodes with storage volumes or monitoring responsibilities. Each node is annotated with metadata such as Nomad datacenter name, domain, supported namespaces, and whether it is suitable for batch processing.

Traefik requires valid TLS certificates in order to expose services over HTTPS. These certificates can be issued by any trusted Certificate Authority (CA) and must cover both wildcard and non-wildcard subdomains based on the selected deployment domain. Once obtained, the certificates should be packaged in a ZIP file and referenced during deployment.

The configuration file "group_vars/all.yml" also includes key deployment parameters such as the path where required files (like certificates) are located, the public IP of the Consul master, the Nomad UI password, and the namespaces to be created. These variables define how the cluster will operate and how services will be exposed.

With everything in place, two Ansible playbooks are executed. The first sets up Consul, which provides service discovery and coordination across the nodes. The second installs and configures Nomad and Traefik, enabling HTTPS access to deployed workloads. Once the playbooks complete successfully, the result is a fully functional Nomad cluster, ready to manage and schedule containerized applications. This procedure sets up the initial cluster, which can later be expanded by deploying additional datacenters and connecting them to this first one to form a federated infrastructure.

Automated deployment using TOSCA

As from [Section 3.1](#), the deployment of the service in a federated environment is fully managed via the TOSCA template, both from IM⁹ and PaaS Orchestrator¹⁰.

Thanks to the support of the graphical interface provided by the dashboard, the user can fill the parameters to properly deploy and configure the Nomad cluster (see [Figure 21](#) for details). The configuration parameters provided are then passed to Ansible for the cluster configuration. The dimension of the Nomad cluster depends on the resources made available by the federated resource provider.

⁸ AI4EOSC GitHub Repository, <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-ansible/tree/master>

⁹ Nomad+Consul, Latest release (IM):

https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/nomad_ai4eosc.yaml

¹⁰ Nomad+Consul, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator):

<https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/nomad.yaml>

Figure 21: View of the Nomad configuration from the PaaS Dashboard.

4.4 - JOIN MY RESOURCES TO THE NOMAD PRODUCTION CLUSTER

Resource provisioning

From an infrastructure perspective, the new datacenter must provision a minimal set of virtual machines, including a Nomad/Consul server node and a Traefik node, both with public IP addresses. Additional client nodes can be added depending on the site's computational needs. As in the initial deployment, all nodes must be reachable via SSH from the control machine that will execute the deployment.

Equally important is the correct configuration of the firewall or security group rules to enable communication between datacenters. Each federation member must explicitly allow both TCP and UDP traffic from the other participating sites. This requires exchanging public IP ranges with all federation peers and updating access policies accordingly. Without this mutual configuration, federated service discovery and scheduling will not function correctly.

Once infrastructure and certificates are ready, the deployment is carried out using the same Ansible repository (with different playbooks) described earlier. The host inventory must be filled to reflect the new nodes and their roles, and the "all.yml" configuration file should be extended to include variables specific to the new datacenter, such as the datacenter name, the IP address of the new server, and the names of the ZIP files containing the federation and Traefik certificates.

As from the previous example, an alternative to resource provisioning provided by the project is the adoption of the TOSCA template from both PaaS Orchestrator¹¹ or IM Dashboard¹² (see [Figure 22](#)).

The screenshot shows the 'Nomad Data' configuration page in the IM Dashboard. The page has a dark header with the 'IM Dashboard' logo and navigation links like 'Infrastructures', 'Advanced', and 'External Links'. The user 'Miguel Caballer' is logged in. The main content area has tabs for 'Server Features', 'WNs Features', 'GPU WNs Features', 'Pub WNs Features', 'Nomad Data', and 'Cloud Provider'. The 'Nomad Data' tab is active, showing a form with the following fields: 'Launch Traefik job as reverse proxy' (dropdown set to 'False'), 'Consul version to install' (text input '1.19.2'), 'Nomad version to install' (text input '1.9.1'), 'Nomad datacenter name' (text input 'ifca-ai4eosc-new'), 'Nomad domain name' (text input 'ifca-new'), 'List of Nomad namespaces' (a list with 'ai4eosc', 'imagine', and 'tutorials', each with a delete icon and a '+ Add' button), 'URL to download the Consul certificates and tokens' (empty text input), 'IP address of the Consul server to join' (empty text input), and 'Primary datacenter of the Consul cluster to join' (text input 'ifca-ai4eosc'). At the bottom, there are 'Submit' and 'Cancel' buttons. The footer shows copyright information '© 2020-2025 GRYPAP' and various icons.

Figure 22: View of the Nomad Join configuration from the IM-Dashboard.

Automated configuration using Ansible

Expanding an existing Nomad federation by adding a new datacenter requires a coordinated process that combines infrastructure provisioning, network configuration, certificate management, and automated deployment. This process builds upon the same Ansible-based framework used for deploying the initial cluster, as described in the previous section.

A key element of the federation model is the use of secure, authenticated communication between datacenters. This is achieved through the use of two distinct types of TLS certificates. The first type corresponds to the Traefik certificates, which are used to expose services over HTTPS and must be issued by a trusted Certificate

¹¹ Nomad+Consul merging existing cluster (PaaS Orchestrator):

https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/nomad/nomad_join.yaml

¹² Nomad+Consul merging existing cluster (IM):

https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/nomad_ai4eosc_join.yaml

Authority. These certificates should cover both the base domain and wildcard subdomains associated with the new site's chosen deployment domain.

The second type consists of the federation certificates, which are used to secure internal communication between the Consul and Nomad servers of different datacenters. These certificates are not publicly issued but instead generated and signed by the administrator of the primary datacenter in the federation. Therefore, before deploying the new site, the administrator must request these internal certificates from the federation's central site. Once received, they are provided in a ZIP archive and used during the deployment process to ensure secure cross-site service discovery and workload orchestration.

Executing the playbooks installs and configures Consul in a federated setup, deploys Nomad with support for multi-datacenter coordination, and enables HTTPS routing via Traefik. Upon completion, the new site becomes a fully functional part of the federation, participating in secure, distributed workload management and service orchestration.

This approach ensures that all federation members are deployed according to a consistent and secure model, reducing complexity and enabling seamless collaboration across sites. By building on a shared Ansible-based automation framework, the integration of new datacenters into the federation remains scalable, repeatable, and maintainable.

4.5 - DEPLOY AN OSCAR CLUSTER

As from the above described service's deployment, an OSCAR cluster can be deployed on any supported IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) Cloud that the user has access to, including public Cloud platforms (e.g. Amazon Web Services [\[AWS\]](#), Microsoft Azure [\[MSAzure\]](#)), and on-premises Cloud Management Platforms (e.g. OpenStack [\[Openstack\]](#), OpenNebula [\[OpenNebula\]](#)) and federated (e.g. EGI [\[EGI\]](#), EOSC EU Node [\[EOSCEUNode\]](#)).

For that, TOSCA templates have been created and adapted, which define the architecture of an OSCAR cluster, which is composed of a Kubernetes cluster and a set of services (e.g. OSCAR Manager, MinIO, NFS, etc.), according to its architecture diagram [\[OSCARArch\]](#). These templates, available in a curated repository of TOSCA templates [\[GRyCAPRepo\]](#), include "oscar.yaml", to deploy an static OSCAR cluster with a user-defined number of nodes, i.e. virtual machines of the Kubernetes cluster, and "oscar-elastic.yaml" to deploy an elastic OSCAR cluster which can grow and shrink in terms of the number of nodes depending on the current workload.

As an example, the deployment of an OSCAR cluster with the IM is step-by-step documented in the "Deployment with IM" [\[OSCARDoc\]](#) section of OSCAR's documentation. It showcases how to use the IM Dashboard, a convenient web-based user interface to facilitate the deployment of infrastructures defined in TOSCA, including OSCAR.

For that, the user can log into the production IM instance operated by UPV [\[IM\]](#), offered as part of the EGI Catalog of services, which demonstrates the commitment of the

AI4EOSC consortium of contributing upstream, to the extent that is possible, the developments done in order to foster sustainability of the developments after the project ends.

Here we include some screenshots for the sake of reference:

First, the user is provided with a catalog of templates, which includes to deploy an OSCAR cluster (see [Figure 23](#))

Figure 23: list of a catalogue of templates from the IM-Dashboard.

Next, the user defines the credentials to access a Cloud on which the OSCAR cluster will be deployed (see [Figure 24](#))

Figure 24: View of the cloud providers from the IM-Dashboard.

Note the integration with the EOSC EU Node so that any European researcher will be able to deploy OSCAR clusters on the infrastructure provided by this initiative from the European Commission with the free renewable credits they offer. Also, note the integration with relevant federated infrastructures such as EGI (the largest federated Cloud in Europe) and Chameleon (a federated testbed from the United States).

The user configures details about the OSCAR cluster such as access passwords, computational requirements and software versions, among others shown in [Figure 25](#).

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Deploy an OSCAR Virtual Cluster". At the top, there is a description: "Deploy an OSCAR Virtual Cluster. (https://grvcao.github.io/oscar/)". Below this, there are several sections:

- Infrastructure Name:** A text input field with the placeholder "description".
- HW Data | OSCAR Data | Cloud Provider Selection:** Three tabs, with "OSCAR Data" currently selected.
- Access Token for the Kubernetes admin user:** A text input field with the placeholder "not_very_secret_token".
- OSCAR password:** A password input field with a strength indicator (8 dots).
- MiniIO password (8 characters min.):** A password input field with a strength indicator (8 dots).
- Email to be used in the Let's Encrypt issuer:** A text input field with the placeholder "jhondoe@server.com".
- ID of the user that creates the infrastructure:** A text input field with the placeholder "0fef2c9370e0f2b4510e1c9b048c115a899dbdb185b946a244d98ed7a4f0a01@egi.eu".
- VO to support:** A dropdown menu with "None" selected.
- Flag to add NVIDIA support:** A dropdown menu with "False" selected.
- Flag to install Apache YuniKorn:** A dropdown menu with "False" selected.

 At the bottom of the form are "Submit" and "Cancel" buttons.

Figure 25: View of the configuration about the OSCAR cluster from the IM-Dashboard.

The lifecycle management of the OSCAR cluster is handled by the IM and displayed in a convenient dashboard, as from [Figure 26](#).

The screenshot shows a dashboard titled "My Infrastructures". It includes a "Refresh" button and a "+ New deployment" button. Below these, there is a search bar and a table with the following columns: Name, Infrastructure uuid, Cloud Type, Cloud Info, Status, VMs, and Actions. The table contains one entry:

Name	Infrastructure uuid	Cloud Type	Cloud Info	Status	VMs	Actions
oscar-aws-1	4b993674-203c-11ef-91ef-5a3710828b91	amazon EC2		pending		Log

 Below the table, it says "Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entry" and there are pagination controls showing page 1 of 1.

Figure 26: View of the OSCAR deployment information from the IM-Dashboard.

The endpoints to access the cluster (see [Figure 27](#)) are automatically provided by the IM. Notice the automated integration with TLS certificates (for https support) and DNS.

Figure 27: View of the OSCAR dashboard.

With this approach, users are provided with an easy-to-use mechanism to self-deploy their own OSCAR clusters on whichever Cloud infrastructure they have access to.

By adopting a similar approach, OSCAR clusters can be deployed by leveraging the integration among the INDIGO PaaS Orchestration system and the IM. In this case, the provider can be chosen from the list of the federated providers and the cluster configuration can be defined via the Orchestrator PaaS Dashboard, similar to what has been described in [Section 4.2](#) and [Section 4.3](#).

5 - CONCLUSION

The present document is a demonstrator of the progress made within the AI4EOOSC project, in particular it describes the tools and services that have been developed and refined in order to be part of the AI4EOOSC 2nd Release.

In particular, the updates related to the implementation plan have been presented in [Section 2](#), supported by a graphical representation of the status of each component.

In [Section 3](#) the status of the main components of the platform has been reported together with the activities performed and the main developments that have been carried out as part of the final release.

In [Section 4](#), instead, an overview of the different deployments, models and services are presented and described, highlighting the easiness of the procedures that have been implemented.

In general, the activities proceeded as expected from the initial plan in order to have all the components ready and the related functionality included in the AI4EOOSC 2nd Release.

REFERENCES

All references were accessed on July 31st 2025.

Endpoints and code of AI4EOSC components are provided in Deliverable 3.4.

[AI4EOSC-D4.1] Marica Antonacci, Álvaro López, Aida Palacio, Ignacio Heredia, Judith Sainz-Pardo, Jaime Céspedes, Germán Moltó, Amanda Calatrava, Miguel Caballer, Viet Tran, Martin Seleng, Stefan Dlugolinsky, Mario David, Daniel San Martín, & Lisana Berberi. (2023). D4.1 - Implementation plan. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7649073>

[AI4EOSC-D4.2] Constantini, A., Donvito, G., Sainz-Pardo, J., Kozlov, V., Tran, V., Dlugolinsky, S., Šeleng, M., & Alarcón, C. (2024). D4.2 - First release of the AI Platform as a Service. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869931>.

[AI4EOSC-D4.3] AI4EOSC Deliverable D4.3, Costantini, A., Sáinz-Pardo, J., Kozlov, V., Dlugolinsky, S., Alarcón, C., & Moltó, G. (2024). D4.3 - WP4 Updated implementation plan and progress report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11485120>

[AI4EOSC/flower] AI4EOSC/flower GitHub repository.

<https://github.com/AI4EOSC/flower/>.

[AI4EOSCResourceFed] INFN Cloud Admin guides,

<https://www.cloud.infn.it/admins-guide/>

[AIRanker] L. Giommi, G. Savarese, G. Vino, D. Ranieri, A. Costantini, G. Donvito, Improving the Cloud Provider Ranking in the INDIGO PaaS Orchestration System Using AI Techniques. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 15886. Springer, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-97576-9_3,

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-97576-9_3

[AIRanker-integration] AI-Ranker integration with INDIGO-PaaS Orcehstrator,

<https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/orchestrator/pull/64>

[AIRankerRelease] AI-Ranker, Latest release (v1.0.0):

<https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/ai-ranker/releases/tag/v1.0.0>

[Ansible] Ansible, <https://docs.ansible.com/>

[AWS] Amazon Web Services, <https://aws.amazon.com/>

[Consul] Consul, <https://www.consul.io/>.

[CVAT1] Periodic CVAT backup implementation.

<https://github.com/ai4os/ai4os-cvat-backups>

[CVAT2] Backup guide on CVAT backuping.

https://docs.cvat.ai/docs/administration/advanced/backup_guide/

[CVAT3] Share path in CVAT.

<https://docs.cvat.ai/docs/administration/basics/installation/#share-path>

[CVAT4] AI4EOSC adjustments made to the original CVAT version 2.28.0.
<https://github.com/cvat-ai/cvat/compare/v2.28.0...ai4os:ai4os-cvat:v2.28.0-AI4OS>

[CVAT5] AI4OS fork of CVAT repository. <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4os-cvat>

[DeploymentPaaSVM] Single VM deployment with persistent volume, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator)
https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/single-vm/single_vm_with_volume.yaml

[DeploymentPaaSdocker] Docker container with persistent volume, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator)
https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/docker/run_docker_with_volume.yaml

[DeploymentIMNomad] Nomad+Consul, Latest release (IM)
https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/nomad_ai4eosc.yaml

[DeploymentPaaSNomad] Nomad+Consul, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator)
<https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/nomad.yaml>

[DeploymentIMOSCAR] OSCAR, Latest release (IM)
<https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/oscar.yaml>

[DeploymentPaaSOSCAR] OSCAR, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator)
<https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/oscar.yaml>

[DeploymentIMNomad+] Nomad+Consul merging existing cluster (IM)
https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/nomad_ai4eosc_join.yaml

[DeploymentPaaSNomad+] Nomad+Consul merging existing cluster (PaaS Orchestrator)
https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/nomad/nomad_join.yaml

[DeploymentPaaSNextCloud] NextCloud deployment (PaaS Orchestrator)
https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/single-vm/cloud_storage_service.yaml

[DocsFlower] AI4OS docs. Federated Learning with Flower.
<https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/federated-flower.html>.

[DocsNVFlare] AI4OS docs. Federated Learning with NVFLARE.
<https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/federated-nvflare.html>.

[EGI] EGI, <https://www.egi.eu/>

[EOSCEUNode] EOSC EU Node, <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

[FedAvgOpt] Sáinz-Pardo Díaz, J. and López García, Á. (2025). Enhancing the Convergence of Federated Learning Aggregation Strategies with Limited Data. arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.15949. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.15949>.

[FederationRegistry] G. Savarese, M. Antonacci, L. Giommi, Federation-registry: the renovated Configuration Management Database for dynamic cloud federation. PoS (ISGC2024) (2024), 021. DOI:10.22323/1.458.0021

[FederationRegistryFeeder] Federation Registry Feeder, <https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/federation-registry-feeder>. Latest release (v1.3.1): <https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/federation-registry-feeder/releases/tag/v1.3.1>

[FederationRegistryRelease] Federation Registry, Latest release (v1.2.1): <https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/federation-registry/releases/tag/v1.2.1>

[Flask] Flask, <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/2.2.x/>

[Flowable] Flowable, <https://www.flowable.com/open-source>.

[Flower] Flower, <https://flower.ai/>

[FLUC1] Sáinz-Pardo Díaz, J. et al (2024). Personalized federated learning for improving radar based precipitation nowcasting on heterogeneous areas. Earth Sci Inform 17, 5561–5584. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12145-024-01438-9>.

[FLUC3] Duda, L. et al. (2025). Exploring Federated Learning for Thermal Urban Feature Segmentation - A Comparison of Centralized and Decentralized Approaches. In: Gervasi, O., et al. Computational Science and Its Applications – ICCSA 2025. ICCSA 2025. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 15648. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-97000-9_18.

[GoAccess] GoAccess, <https://goaccess.io/>

[Grafana] Grafana, <https://grafana.com/>

[GRyCAPRepo] GRyCAP's repository of TOSCA Templates. <https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/>

[Horovod] Horovod, <https://horovod.ai/>

[IM] Infrastructure Manager, <https://www.grycap.upv.es/im>. Latest release (v1.19.0): <https://github.com/grycap/im/releases/tag/v1.19.0>

[INDIGO-IAM] INDIGO-IAM service, <https://github.com/indigo-iam/iam>. Latest release (v1.12.0): <https://github.com/indigo-iam/iam/tree/v1.12.0>

[INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator] Costantini A. et al. (2021) A Cloud-Edge Orchestration Platform for the Innovative Industrial Scenarios of the IoTwins Project. In: Gervasi O. et al. (eds) Computational Science and Its Applications – ICCSA 2021. ICCSA 2021. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 12950. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86960-1_37

[INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator Dashboard Release] INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator Dashboard. Last release (v.4.5.1): <https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/orchestrator-dashboard/releases/tag/v4.5.1>

[INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator Release] INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator. Last release (v.4.2.1): <https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/orchestrator/releases/tag/v4.2.1>

[Jenkins AI4EOSC] Jenkins AI4EOSC, <https://jenkins.services.ai4os.eu/>

[Kafka] Kafka, <https://kafka.apache.org/>.

[Keycloak] Keycloak, <https://www.keycloak.org/>

[MinIO] MinIO, <https://www.min.io/>

[MLFlow] MIFlow, <https://mlflow.org/>.

[MSAzure] Microsoft Azure, <https://azure.microsoft.com/>

[MySQL] MySQL used for the INDIGO PaaS Dashboard, <https://www.mysql.com/it/>

[NextCloud] Nextcloud, <https://nextcloud.com/it/>

[Nomad] Nomad, <https://www.nomadproject.io/>.

[NVFlare] NVFlare, <https://developer.nvidia.com/flare>

[OIDC] OpenID Connect, <https://openid.net/developers/how-connect-works/>.

[OAuth2.0] Oauth 2.0, <https://oauth.net/2/>.

[OpenNebula] OpenNebula, <https://openebula.io/>

[Openstack] Openstack, <https://www.openstack.org/>

[OSCARArch] OSCAR Architecture & Components.
<https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/latest/#architecture-components>

[OSCARDoc] OSCAR documentation. "Deployment with IM".
<https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/latest/deploy-im-dashboard/>

[Prometheus] Prometheus, <https://prometheus.io/>

[React] React, <https://react.dev/>

[Robot] Robot Framework, <https://react.dev/>

[TOSCA] TOSCA OASIS Standard,
https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=tosca.

[Traefik] Traefik, <https://traefik.io/traefik>

